

VARCLIREFOR

FORWARDS project

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Deliverable 1.2: VARCLIREFOR Final technical report

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Preface

This Deliverable 1.2 describes the methods applied in the VARCLIREFOR project, funded within the FORWARDS consortium.

The VARCLIREFOR project was conducted between May 2024 (M1) and August 2025 (M16) in the Utrechtse Heuvelrug area, which is a ca. 20,000 ha large forest area found in the central part of the Netherlands. The forests on the Utrechtse Heuvelrug are dominated by *P. sylvestris*, but local co-dominance of other species occur like *P. menziesii*, *B. pendula*, *Q. robur* and *F. sylvatica*. Most forest is located on former sandy (glacial) moraines, and soils are highly affected by continuous nitrogen deposition from traffic, industry and agriculture, soil acidification and increasing drought periods due to climate change. In most areas, only deep ground water levels are found, indicating most of the forest is solely rain fed and phreatic water stored in the upper soil layers are the most important water sources for vegetation growth.

The VARCLIREFOR project studied survival and growth of naturally regenerated and planted tree saplings in new field trials in one experimental site on the Utrechtse Heuvelrug area. Furthermore, patterns in soil factors in existing forest plots within the larger forest area where studied.

New trials (new forest and sapling plots) were located in one of the Forest Management Units (FMU) of the Dutch State Forestry Service (FMU unit 'AUS'), while the existing trials ca. 781 forest plots) were located in three separate FMUs ('AUS', 'AML' and 'VUU').

Data collected during the execution of VARCLIREFOR are stored in datafiles and uploaded to the Forest Observatory of FORWARDS.

The authors

Table of contents

Preface	2
1. Introduction	4
2. Plot setup and sapling planting in WP2.....	6
2.1 Existing plots within the WP2 working area.....	6
2.2 Additional semi-permanent plots	6
2.2.1 Additional plot level data	7
2.2.2 Tree level data of alive and standing dead trees	9
2.2.3 Lying dead wood	10
2.2.4 Natural regeneration	11
2.3 Sapling planting.....	11
2.3.1 Sapling treatment.....	13
2.3.2 Sapling measurements.....	14
2.4 Natural recruitment measurements	15
3. Soil sampling and field measurements	16
3.1 Soil sampling in WP2	16
3.2 Soil sampling in WP3	16
3.3 Litter collection and processing in WP3.....	16
3.4 Light availability	16
3.5 Decomposition measurements.....	17
3.5.1 Tea Bag Preparation, deployment, and processing.....	17
3.5.2 Decomposition time series	18
3.5.3 Tea Bag Index parameter calculations	20
3.6 Soil fauna feeding activity	20
4. Soil and nutrient processing.....	23
4.1 Soil Analyses	23
4.1.1 Soil pH.....	23
4.1.2 Anorganic nitrogen: NO _x , NO ₃ , NO ₂ , NH ₄ , PO ₄	24
4.1.3 Cation concentrations	24
4.1.4 Soil organic carbon and C:N ratio	24
4.1.5 Soil Organic Matter Content	25
5. WP 3 Forest plot data, processing and calculations	26
5.1. Plot layout existing field trials (WP3).....	26
5.2 Tree growth measurements.....	26
5.3 Allometric relations	27

1. Introduction

The VARCLIREFOR project consists of two work packages, each with its unique aim and methodologies. This deliverable describes the applied methods (field and laboratory techniques) carried out in the work packages 2 and 3. All data were collected in the National Park Utrechtse Heuvelrug in three forest management units: Vuursche (VUU), Austerlitz (AUS) and Amerongen-Leersum (AML).

WP2

Work package 2 focused on newly established field trials in the forest management unit of Austerlitz, designed to evaluate tree species that may be better adapted to the increasingly dry conditions of the Utrechtse Heuvelrug. In these experimental plots, saplings of various species were planted in a controlled setup. Among these are so-called “rich litter species” — species known to produce nutrient-rich litter that may contribute to the development of a more favorable organic layer in the soil. This layer plays a key role in supporting soil biodiversity and improving nutrient cycling, potentially enhancing soil quality and ecosystem resilience under changing climatic conditions. The experimental setup consisted of the addition of a combination of nutrients and mycorrhiza in the planting holes of planted saplings to support the growing conditions.

To better understand the growing conditions for the planted saplings, a range of soil and environmental parameters were measured within the plots. These include canopy cover, soil organic matter content, pH, soil organic carbon and CN ratio, $\text{NH}_4\text{-N}$, $\text{NO}_3\text{-N}$, $\text{NO}_2\text{-N}$ and $\text{NO}_x\text{-N}$ and several cations. Additionally, soil decomposition activity was assessed using the Tea Bag Index (TBI), which provides insight into microbial activity and organic matter breakdown in the topsoil.

Alongside the planted saplings, the natural regeneration of tree species was monitored over a period of four months, with a focus on height growth and survival.

The working area of WP2 also contained a range of existing plots that offer historical data on tree diameter at breast height (DBH) and historical growth. A subset of these plots also contain data on dead trees, lying dead wood and rejuvenation.

WP3

Work Package 3 focuses on tree growth-, soil- and environmental data from three forest management units on the Utrechtse Heuvelrug: Vuursche, Austerlitz, and Amerongen-Leersum. As in WP2, a comprehensive set of parameters was collected to characterize site conditions, in a random set of 150 plots. Sampling in these plots included litter biomass, canopy cover, soil organic matter content (SOM), pH, soil organic carbon and C/N ratio, concentrations of $\text{NH}_4\text{-N}$, $\text{NO}_3\text{-N}$, $\text{NO}_2\text{-N}$ and $\text{NO}_x\text{-N}$ and in a sub-set of these selected plots, various cation concentrations. In WP3, bait lamina strips were used in addition to the Tea Bag Index (TBI) method to measure decomposition rates, providing information on the feeding activity of soil invertebrates. These measurements provide a baseline for understanding how local abiotic factors influence forest dynamics and soil processes across different forest stands.

The field measurements are complemented by long-term plot data on tree growth measurements derived from ca 800 plots in these three forest management units. These data included diameter at breast height (DBH) measurements recorded in three different years that covered a time span of roughly 30 years, and tree height measurements of a selection of trees in these plots. This dataset allows for the analysis of growth trends over time in relation to environmental variables. In addition,

historical meteorological data were integrated to help interpret how long-term climatic conditions may have influenced forest development and site productivity.

2. Plot setup and sapling planting in WP2

2.1 Existing plots within the WP2 working area

The WP2 working area includes 11 plots that fall within the same grid of plots as the WP3 plots as described in section 5.1. Data in these plots is collected using the same methodology as in the plots of WP3 in three different periods (1994, 2006, 2019). In 2023, using the same methodology, 23 new plots were established and monitored for tree DBH of ca. 20 trees. The original plots have the format Location_LetterNumber (AUS_G18), the new 2023 plots have the format Location_number (AUS_1). Note that in these plots, data on the exact location of individual trees was not collected.

In 2024, 38 additional semi-permanent plots were installed in the WP2 working area, using a slightly different monitoring methodology that allows for individual tree monitoring, as described in section 2.2.

Table 2.1: Overview of plot types and used monitoring methodology in the WP2 working area.

Plot type	Methodology	Individual tree location recorded
Existing plots (1994, 2006, 2019)	See section 5.1.	No
2023 existing plots	See section 5.1.	No
Additional semi-permanent plots	See section 2.2.	Yes

2.2 Additional semi-permanent plots

In November and December 2024 (M7-M8 of the project), 38 new semi-permanent circular plots were installed in the forest management unit of Austerlitz. The plots are located in 11 'demonstration stands', i.e. in 7 stands dominated by *Pinus sylvestris* (Scots pine) (28 plots total) and 4 stands dominated by *Quercus rubra* (American oak) (10 plots total) (see Figure 2.1). Measurements took place at plot level and at tree level, as described below.

Figure 2.1: Location of 38 semi-permanent circular plots in the FMU of Austerlitz, established in Nov-Dec 2024.

2.2.1 Additional plot level data

In Austerlitz, in each demonstration stand a 1 ha area was defined in which 2 or 4 circular plots were installed. Circular plots consisted of 15m radius circles and nested 8m radius circles (see Figure 2.2).

Figure 2.2: The semi-permanent circular plots consist of a circle with 15m radius in which trees ≥ 10 cm DBH were measured and a smaller circle with 8m radius in which trees ≥ 5 cm DBH were measured.

Per plot the following was determined:

- coordinates of the center
- year of origin
- dominant tree species
- average height of 2-4 individuals of dominant species
- development phase of the vegetation, i.e. successional stage
- canopy cover

Coordinates of the center of each plot were recorded with a GPS. The year of origin/establishment was estimated based on data of the state forest service. The dominant tree species was determined and defined as the tree species that is most abundant. Height of 2-4 individuals of the dominant species was determined by using laser equipment and averaged. The development phase of the forest consists of several classes of successional stages:

Table 2.2: classification of successional stages

Class	Successional stage
1	open phase (no trees)
2	establishment phase (young trees present)
3	thicket phase
4	pole stage (closed forest)
5	tree/climax phase
6	deterioration phase

We determined canopy cover from the center point of three individual trees that were measured for extra traits in May 2025 (see 2.2.2). Canopy cover was measured with the CanopyApp available at the AppleStore, at a height of 1.8m.

Additionally, in the 8m radius plots the following was measured:

- tree cover
- shrub cover

The tree cover (above 6m) and shrub cover (0.5-6m) consist of the following percentage classes:

Table 2.3: percentage classes of tree and shrub cover

Code	Cover in %
1	0-0.1
2	0.1-1
3	1-5
4	5-10
5	10-25
6	25-50
7	50-75
8	75-90
9	90-100

2.2.2 Tree level data of alive and standing dead trees

Within the 15m radius circle plots for trees with a dbh ≥ 10 cm and within the nested 8m radius circle plots for trees with a dbh ≥ 5 cm, the following variables were measured:

- species
- DBH
- angle and distance from center

Each tree was identified to species level and DBH was measured with a caliper. The location of each tree was determined using the polar coordinate system. The distance from the centre of the plot to the tree (centre of the trunk base) was measured with a measuring taper. The deviation (angle) of each tree is determined clockwise (right) in degrees relative to north using a compass, where north is at 0°.

Standing dead trees were also measured in the 15m radius circle plots. Standing dead wood was measured in the same way as the alive standing trees but are recorded on a separate tab in the datafile.

In March 2025 (M13) we selected 3 random trees in/near each plot for additional measurements including:

- crown dimensions

- increment
- defoliation (i.e vitality)

Crown dimensions were determined with a length tape by measuring the extent of the crown along the NW and SE axes. For increment we measured dbh with a diameter tape and spray-painted a blue ring around the tree. We will measure dbh again in May 2026 on that exact spot. Defoliation/vitality was determined by using ‘vitality classes’ (Lerink et al 2023).

Table 2.4: tree vitality classes

Vitality class	Description
1	vital tree, good leaf coverage, intact tree without major cracks or loose bark
2	reduction in vitality, clearly reduced leaf or needle occupation, broken top
3	nearly dead tree, dropped majority of needles or leaves, large damage
4	no needles or leaves left

2.2.3 Lying dead wood

Lying dead wood was measured along 3 transects within the 15m radius circle plots (see Figure 2.3).

Figure 2.3: Dead wood on the forest floor was measured along three transects.

Along each transect pieces of dead wood larger than 10cm in diameter at the thickest end, and with a diameter of more than 5cm at the intersection with the transect, were measured. Species, diameters at the thickest end (in classes) and at the intersections (continuous data), length (in classes: 1 for <10m and 2 for >10m) and decomposition class were recorded.

Table 2.5: Tree diameter classes

Class	Diameter at thickest end
1	<30cm
2	30-40cm
3	40-50cm
4	50-60cm

Table 2.6: Tree decomposition classes

Decomposition class	Description
1	Tree recently fell, wood is still hard
2	Bark starts peeling off, wood can be indented up to 1 cm with a knife
3	Bark mostly peeled off. Wood can be indented a few centimeters with a knife (especially sapwood; heartwood still partly hard).
4	Largely decayed: the entire log is rotten, soft, and crumbling.

2.2.4 Natural regeneration

In the circles with 8m radius, for trees <5cm dbh (i.e. rejuvenation) the number of individuals per species were counted and grouped by length (<20 cm, >20-80 cm, >80-130 cm and >130 cm). The number of individuals with damage was recorded.

2.3 Sapling planting

Saplings of 14 species were planted in the 40-hectare demonstration site forest management unit in February 2025 (M10). Due to shortage of planting material that was purchased in the end of 2024, only 3,430 individuals could be planted.

Planting was done in monoculture groups of 25 individuals (or 5 individuals for 1 species, i.e. *Taxus baccata*), with one to two meters between each individual. All saplings were planted within fenced areas to prevent browsing by herbivores (Figure 2.4).

Figure 2.4: Saplings are planted in most fenced areas (indicated by red), except for areas 12–14, where natural regeneration will be promoted by fencing to exclude herbivores.

Table 2.7: Overview of the tree species planted in Austerlitz. For each species, the table specifies the designated planting location (see also Figure 2.4), the number of individuals planted in each area, the total number of planting groups and saplings per species, and the number we labelled and measured for growth and survival.

Latin name	Planting location	Number of individuals per planting area	Amount of planting groups per species	Total number of saplings per species	Growth and survival measurements
<i>Abies bornmuelleriana</i>	1, 10	100, 100	8	200	120 (8 planting groups x 15 monitored saplings per planting group)
<i>Acer campestre</i>	3, 4, 6	50, 50, 100	8	200	120 (8 x 15)
<i>Acer platanoides</i>	6, 9, 10	100, 50, 50	8	200	120 (8 x 15)
<i>Acer pseudoplatanus</i>	1, 6, 9, 10	100, 150, 100, 50	16	400	240 (16 x 15)
<i>Betula pubescens</i>	5, 6, 7	50, 100, 100	10	250	150 (10 x 15)
<i>Carpinus betulus</i>	1, 6, 10	100, 150, 100	14	350	210 (14 x 15)
<i>Castanea sativa</i>	5, 6, 7	100, 50, 50	8	200	120 (8 x 15)
<i>Cedrus libani</i>	7, 8, 9	100, 50, 100	10	250	150 (10 x 15)
<i>Pinus nigra</i>	7, 9	150, 100	10	250	150 (10 x 15)
<i>Prunus avium</i>	1, 4, 6	100, 50, 100	10	250	150 (10 x 15)
<i>Quercus petraea</i>	3, 5, 7, 8	50, 100, 100, 50	12	300	180 (12 x 15)
<i>Quercus robur</i>	6, 9	100, 100	8	200	120 (8 x 15)
<i>Taxus baccata</i>	5, 6, 9, 10	20, 20, 20, 20	16	80	80 (16 groups x 5 monitored saplings per planting group)
<i>Thuja plicata</i>	5, 6, 9, 10	100, 50, 50, 100	12	300	180 (12 x 15)
TOTAL			150	3430	2090

2.3.1 Sapling treatment

Within each planting group, six saplings were inoculated with mycorrhiza, and three saplings also received additional nutrients, while the other three saplings did not. The remaining 19 saplings per group were not inoculated; 16 of these received nutrients, and three did not (see Figure 2.5). One species, *Taxus baccata*, followed a different design and was planted in groups of five individuals. All individuals that were part of the experiment were labelled with a tag.

Figure 2.5. Overview of the experimental design showing the distribution of treatments and measured saplings within one group of 25 planted saplings. For *Taxus baccata* the number of saplings receiving the treatments are 2-1-1-1.

Nutrient addition treatment:

A mixture of approximately 750 grams of Eifelgold rock flour and 250 grams of calcium-magnesium carbonate was applied to the soil that had been removed during soil drilling. The amended soil was then used to refill the planting hole during planting.

Mycorrhizal inoculation treatment:

Saplings were inoculated with either endo- or ectomycorrhiza, based on the tree species' preference for one of these types. The endomycorrhizal inoculation followed a similar procedure as with nutrient supplementation. Eight grams Symbivit endomycorrhizal granules were evenly sprinkled on the removed soil, which was returned to the planting hole during planting. For ectomycorrhizal inoculation, a liquid inoculum was prepared according to the manufacturer's instructions (Tuinenshop.nl, n.d.) using Symbivit ectomycorrhiza. Roots of saplings were dipped into this solution prior to planting.

2.3.2 Sapling measurements

During the weeks after planting (March 2025, M11), the initial diameter and stem length of all labelled saplings were measured, comprising 60% of all planted individuals per species, and 100% for *Taxus baccata*. Diameter measurements were done at 10cm above the soil surface using a caliper, while sapling height was measured from the soil to the tip of the growing shoot or bud using a measuring tape.

In M14 (June 2025) the diameter and height measurements were repeated on the individuals that were alive. We also recorded which individuals died.

At M11 and M14 canopy cover was measured using the CanopyApp available from the Apple store. Openness was measured at a height of 1,8m in the center of each planting group.

2.4 Natural recruitment measurements

In addition to the natural regeneration that was measured in the additional semi-permanent plots (see 2.2.4) we measured regenerating trees in another set of plots, also in the FMU of Austerlitz. These 1m² plots were part of another experiment, not part of VARCLIREFOR (see Lembrechts, 2025). Half of the plots (i.e. 20) were located in an enclosure, to prevent them from herbivory, while the other half (i.e. 21) were not fenced (see Figure 2.5).

Figure 2.5: The project area Austerlitz, where each pin represents a plot location of 1 x 1 m. The blue and green pins represent plots where natural regeneration measurements took place. The red and purple plots were not used in this study. The plots are positioned according to the EcoFracNet setup (Lembrechts, 2025). Additional plots (green) were placed inside of herbivore enclosures. All plots inside of the white lines are located inside of enclosures.

In all 41 plots, young trees were labelled and identified (<2 m height) to species level (M10, February 2025). Tree height was measured from the base of the stem at soil level to the highest living point of the stem. Diameter was measured using a calliper placed at half the total height of the sapling. During the second measurement (M13, May 2025), diameter was measured at the same height point as in M10 for each individual sapling, ensuring consistency across time points. A total of 168 naturally regenerated trees of 12 different species were identified, labelled and measured in M10.

Canopy cover was measured in each plot in M10 and M13 with the CanopyApp available at the AppleStore, at a height of 1.8m.

3. Soil sampling and field measurements

3.1 Soil sampling in WP2

In the WP2 experimental location and the new field trial section a selection of the 153 planted sapling groups was made so that 64 groups were selected for soil analyses. Five planting groups per species were randomly selected for sampling. In total, 65 soil samples were collected during the initial measurement period.

Soil was extracted at four different points within the planting group using a soil auger, collecting the top 20 cm of soil. These four subsamples were combined to form one composite sample per group. To ensure our measurements were not influenced by the treatments given to the saplings, the samples were taken at least 0.5m away from the planted saplings.

Upon arrival at the laboratory, all soil samples were stored at 4°C in a cold room to preserve their physiochemical properties for subsequent analyses.

3.2 Soil sampling in WP3

In WP3, a total of ca. 800 semi-permanent plots exist in the three forest management units, and a stratified random selection of 150 plots were made in such way that for each FMU ca 50 plots were sampled for soil properties. Environmental data was collected to assess abiotic factors influencing decomposition dynamics. Soil samples and light availability measurements were taken directly in the field, while additional data on forest structure and composition of the established plots were earlier provided by the State Forestry Service.

In each of the 150 selected plots three soil samples were collected using a cylindrical auger. For each of the three soil sub-samples, the organic matter layer thickness was measured with a taper and recorded in the field before extracting the top 20 cm of soil. The sub-samples were then combined into a single composite sample per plot and put in labeled plastic bags for transport.

Upon arrival at the laboratory, all soil samples were stored at 4°C in a cold room to preserve their physiochemical properties for subsequent analyses.

3.3 Litter collection and processing in WP3

In each of the 150 existing plots, two litter samples were taken, for which each sub-sample a 25x25 cm grid was placed on the forest floor and all litter material (leaves, twigs, seeds) were collected and put in a plastic bag. The bags were stored at 4°C in a cold room for further processing.

Litter samples were separated in fractions of leaves, twigs and seeds. After separation, all sub samples were oven dried (Thermo Scientific Heratherm OMS180) at 45°C for 48 hours and weighed afterwards to determine the dry weight of each litter fraction.

3.4 Light availability

For the 150 existing plots light availability was measured using a densiometer (Baudry et al., 2013). Three measurements were taken per plot to assess tree canopy density. The percentage of covered canopy was determined by recording the proportion of squares on the densiometer without

vegetation, which was then multiplied by a correction factor (1.04) to estimate total canopy cover. The three measurements were averaged to obtain one canopy cover parameter for the plot.

3.5 Decomposition measurements

Due to problems in the supply of Beta-glucosidase enzymes for decomposition experiments, the Tea-Bag Index (TBI) methodology was applied to measure in-field decomposition rates. The TBI is a standardized method used to assess early-stage organic matter decomposition and stabilization in soils and sediments (Keuskamp et al., 2013). It involves burying bags containing green and rooibos tea—representing labile and recalcitrant plant materials, respectively—for a fixed period. Changes in mass over time are used to calculate decomposition rates and stabilization factors.

The standard green tea as used in the research by Keuskamp et al. (2013) (Lipton Indonesian tea Sencha tradition, EAN8722700055525) is no longer available, and alternative green tea is only available in degradable bags. We therefore transferred the tea from degradable bags to self-made mesh bags with the same mesh size as the original tea bags as prescribed for the TBI (200 micron). We used an alternative green tea that is prescribed as a suitable alternative by the Tea Bag Index organization (Lipton Japanese Sencha: EAN 5063270101797). However, the authors of the earlier mentioned TBI research are still developing suitable parameters to derive k and S values from decomposition data of this tea. For the most accurate k and S calculations, these parameters can be recalculated using updated parameters in the future. However, due to a change in testing material (new type of green tea), a decomposition time series test had to be applied.

Green and Rooibos mesh bags were buried in duplo in each of the 150 existing field trials (2 green, 2 rooibos). In the new field trials in Austerlitz where the saplings were planted, one rooibos and one green tea mesh bag was buried in each of the 64 plots where also soil measurements were performed.

3.5.1 Tea Bag Preparation, deployment, and processing

Mesh bags were constructed using 200-micron nylon mesh, which was cut into uniform squares (approximately 5 cm x 5 cm), with three sides glued together using hot glue, leaving one side open for adding litter.

Each mesh bag contained ca. 3 g of green tea (representing labile material) and one containing ca. 3 g of rooibos tea (representing recalcitrant material). Exact tea weights were recorded a-priori using a precision balance. Each bag was labeled with a unique identifier indicating location, plot, and tea type (“G” for green tea, and “R” for rooibos tea). The weight of each completed mesh bag was also measured and recorded.

In the field, the teabags were buried per plot using standardized protocol. Teabags were buried approximately 1-1.5 m North from the plot’s central tree. Bags were buried at the soil surface at a uniform depth of approximately 20 cm, and 15 cm apart in a square. Each burial location was marked with a skewer and the central tree was marked with a ribbon to facilitate retrieval. Litterbags remained in situ for exactly 91 days. Exact burial and retrieval dates can be found in table 3.1.

Table 3.1: burial and retrieval dates of mesh tea bags

IN: Mesh tea bags	OUT: Mesh tea bags
25-4-2025	25-7-2025
28-4-2025	28-7-2025
29-4-2025	29-7-2025
30-4-2025	30-7-2025
2-5-2025	1-8-2025
7-5-2025	6-8-2025
8-5-2025	7-8-2025
9-5-2025	8-8-2025
12-5-2025	11-8-2025
13-5-2025	12-8-2025

After exactly 91 days, mesh bags were retrieved in the same order as their deployment to ensure temporal consistency. Using a shovel, teabags were carefully removed, and adhering soil particles were brushed off in the field. Retrieved bags were placed in sealed containers and transported to the lab to prevent contamination or further decomposition during transit.

In the lab, all soil particles were removed from the outside of the bags. Mesh bags were then carefully opened and the contents were spread out over a large paper sheet, allowing for identification and removal of ingrown root material. were placed in separate paper cups for drying and weighing. The tea in paper cups was oven-dried at 70°C for 48 hours to standardize moisture content.

After removal out of the oven, warm tea attracts moist from the air. The increase in weight due to moisture attraction within the first 10 minutes was considered negligible. Therefore, each paper cup was removed from the oven separately and weighed immediately after. The final dry weight of the material was then measured using a precision balance.

Two compensations factors affecting decomposition needed to take place. First, the tea before deployment was not dried in the oven at 70°C for 48 hours in advance, as was done with the tea after deployment. We did follow this process for 5 tea samples to determine an average moisture content in the green tea. The average of this moisture content was used to compensate the weights before deployment with.

$$\text{Dried tea BEFORE} = \text{Moist weight tea BEFORE} * \text{average moisture \%}$$

A second compensation was applied for possible influx of very small soil particles that may have passed through the 200 micron mesh openings. In 15 plots we therefore buried a bag and retrieved it directly after. These bags were brushed of carefully, contents were emptied in a paper cup, dried at 70°C for 48 hours and compensated for soil moisture. Any increase in weight that was recorded was deemed influx of soil particles in the mesh bags. These weight differences were averaged to obtain a compensation factor for soil influx.

$$\text{Soil compensated tea AFTER} = \text{Dried weight tea AFTER} * \text{average soil influx \%}$$

3.5.2 Decomposition time series

After a certain amount of time all labile fractions in green tea have decomposed and the weight stabilizes, after which the parameters in section 3.5.3. can be calculated. In order to check whether the weight loss of green tea indeed stabilized over time, several time series were done. Teabags of

japanese sencha, indonesian sencha and rooibos were buried in 5 different plots. In each plot 5 bags were buried and retrieved after 7, 14, 29, 68 or 130 days. The weight loss of each bag was recorded.

The time series setup was based on the research by Keuskamp et al. (2013) and measurement days were chosen accordingly; teabags were measured at 0, 4, 7, 14, 29, 68 and 130 days. For the green tea used in this experiment, Japanese sencha, a stabilization of decomposition took place between 67 and 130 days as shown in table 3.2.

Figure 3. 1 shows the time series plot, showing the fraction of remaining tea over time. Individual points represent observed values from each experimental plot. The lines represent the monotonic means per tea type. The Japanese green sencha tea as used in this experiment meets the necessary assumption that green tea decomposition stabilizes after 90 days, with no further significant decomposition. With this assumption met, decomposition parameters can be calculated.

Table 3.2: Tea bag index time series average results of remaining tea weight fractions over time for different tea types.

Days	Rooibos remaining fraction	Japanese Green remaining fraction	Indonesian Green remaining fraction
0	1.00	1.00	1.00
4	1.00	0.94	0.92
7	0.98	0.89	0.89
14	0.91	0.71	0.67
29	0.85	0.53	0.54
68	0.80	0.35	0.39
130	0.63	0.32	0.30

Figure 3.1: Tea bag index time series results for different tea types. Individual points represent the remaining fractions in each of the 5 time series plots. Lines represent the monotonic means through these points.

3.5.3 Tea Bag Index parameter calculations

The TBI results in two parameters that together describe the decomposition in the soil: the stabilization factor S and the decomposition rate k . The stabilization factor is calculated as following:

$$S = 1 - \left(\frac{ag}{Hg}\right)$$

Where:

- S = Stabilisation factor
- ag = fraction of decomposed green tea
- Hg = hydrolysable fraction of green tea

The decomposition rate k is calculated as following:

$$k = \frac{\text{Ln}\left(\frac{ar}{Wt - (1 - ar)}\right)}{t}$$

In which =

$$ar = Hr * (1 - S)$$

Where:

- k = decomposition rate
- ar = predicted labile fraction red tea
- Wt = fraction remaining red tea
- t = burial period
- Hr = hydrolysable fraction of red tea
- S = stabilization factor

It is important to note that the hydrolysable fraction of both green and red tea for the tea types used are not yet up to date, and based on the original tea types as prescribed by Keuskamp et al. (2023). When updated parameters become available through their research, the k and S can be updated with the tea weight loss data that is provided.

Also: in some plots k or S could not be calculated. According to the authors of the Tea Bag Index this is a result of a fast breakdown of labile material in the rooibos teabags, in which the tea moves from the first to the second phase of decomposition. The formula will then calculate a negative k or no k at all.

3.6 Soil fauna feeding activity

The bait lamina test was used to complement decomposition experiments to the extent to assess soil faunal feeding activity in each plot. This method involves filling standardized strips with bait material to measure feeding activity via perforation consumption over time (Kratz, 1998). Two strips were deployed per plot. This action was performed two times, in 2024 and 2025, with some overlap in plots.

The bait material was prepared by mixing a standardized substrate consisting of 70% cellulose, 25% wheat bran, and 5% activated carbon. For this study, oats were used as the wheat bran source and were ground into fine particles using a series of sieves with decreasing mesh sizes (0.5 mm, 0.2 mm, and finally 0.12 mm). The activated carbon was sourced from Norit pills, which were crushed into a fine powder using a spoon to achieve the desired consistency. The prepared dry components were then thoroughly mixed to ensure uniform distribution. Distilled water was gradually added to the mixture to form a paste-like consistency suitable for filling the bait lamina strips. The bait material was then stored in an airtight container to maintain its moisture and consistency until it was applied to the strips.

The bait lamina strips were constructed using standardized polyvinyl chloride (PVC) strips with 16 evenly spaced perforations (2 mm diameter) along their length. The empty strips were aligned on an aluminum sheet and taped at the upper portion of each strip (above the perforations) to keep them in place. The prepared bait mixture was applied directly onto the perforated area of the strips using a spatula. The bait was pressed firmly against the strips to ensure that each perforation was completely filled. This process was repeated for all strips. Excess bait on the surface of the strips was carefully wiped away to prevent obstruction or contamination during deployment.

Once all perforations were filled, the strips were placed in an oven set at 40°C for 48 hours to dry the bait within the holes. After drying, any holes that had lost bait (as the material is fragile and can fall out during handling) were refilled following the same procedure. The strips were then dried again to secure the bait in place. After fully prepared, strips were stored in a labeled plastic container to protect them from moisture or damage until deployment.

In the field, two bait lamina strips were deployed per plot, with strips placed on opposite sides of the plot's central tree to account for spatial variability. Strips were inserted vertically into the soil using a small slit made with a trowel. Insertion depth was such that the topmost hole was just below ground level ensuring that the perforations were buried at uniform and exposed to the same environmental conditions. A marker was placed near each strip for identification during retrieval. Strips remained in the soil for two weeks, allowing adequate time for soil fauna to interact with the bait. Exact burial and retrieval dates for the 2025 dataset can be found in table 3.3.

Table 3.3: Burial and retrieval dates of bait lamina strips in the 2025 measuring series.

IN: Bait lamina 2025	OUT: bait lamina 2025
26-6-2025	10-7-2025
30-6-2025	14-7-2025
11-6-2025	25-6-2025
24-6-2025	8-7-2025
13-6-2025	27-6-2025
25-6-2025	9-7-2025

After two weeks, strips were retrieved in the same order as their deployment. Strips were carefully taken out of the soil to avoid disturbing the bait or altering the perforations. Retrieval was performed systematically to ensure consistency, with each strip being gently removed and immediately assessed for bait consumption. For each perforation (16 in total), data was recorded as follows:

- "0" for an empty hole (bait fully consumed)
- "0.5" for a half-filled hole (bait partially consumed)
- "1" for a full hole (no bait consumed)

For each plot, the strip was divided in four depth sections: hole 1-4-, hole 5-8, hole 9-12, hole 13-16. For each groups the proportion of non-filled/filled was determined, which is a measure for the feeding activity. This was also done for the whole strip in total. The results for both strips were averaged to obtain an average total feeding activity per plot as well as average feedings activities per depth section per plot.

4. Soil and nutrient processing

Soil and nutrient analysis was conducted in laboratories at the faculty of Geosciences and Natural Sciences, Utrecht University, using standardized protocols to ensure consistency and reliability. An overview of types of measurements, methods and used equipment can be found in table 4.1.

Table 4.1: Overview of applied methods of soil, litter and decomposition analysis.

Measurement	Method	Equipment	Unit
pH	Measurement of soil in KCl extract	Mettler Toledo SevenCompact Duo	pH (KCl)
C:N ratio	Analysis of dried, ground and acidified soil samples	Heto PowerDry LL3000; SCALA TFD5503;CN-analyzer (NA1500, Fisons Instruments); Herzog HP-Ma automatic pulverizer	Soil C/N ratio, soil C (%) and soil N (%)
Soil Organic Matter	Calculated as weight loss after 4 hours heating at 550°C	Heto PowerDry LL3000; SCALA TFD5503TGA701; Thermogravimetric Analyzer	Soil organic Matter (%)
NH ₄ -N, NH ₃ -N, NH ₂ -N, NO _x -N, PO ₄ -P	Sample in KCl in discrete analyzer	Thermo Fisher Scientific Gallery	NO _x -N (mg N/kg soil) PO ₄ -P (mg P/kg soil)
Al, Ca, Fe, K, Mg, Na		Heto PowerDry LL3000;SCALA TFD5503; Herzog HP-Ma automatic pulverizer, Perkin-Elmer Avio 500 ICP-OES	Al, Ca, Fe, K, Mg, Na (mg/L)
Litter	Oven drying	Thermo Scientific Heratherm OMS180, precision balance	Biomass (g/m ² surface area)
Teabags	Oven drying	Thermo Scientific Heratherm OMS180, precision balance	g

4.1 Soil Analyses

Soil samples were analyzed to determine their physical and chemical properties using the following methods:

4.1.1 Soil pH

Soil pH was measured using a 1 M KCl solution to assess exchangeable acidity (Van Reeuwijk, 1992). 20 mL of 1M KCl was added to exactly 8 grams of soil in a 50 mL Greiner tube. The mixture was shaken for 2 hours using a reciprocating shaker. The suspension was centrifuged and the electrode was

immersed in the supernatant. The soil pH (pH-KCl) was measured using a Mettler Toledo SevenCompact Duo pH meter. pH readings were recorded once stabilized (± 0.1 unit accuracy), with fluctuations not exceeding 0.1 unit per 30 seconds.

4.1.2 Anorganic nitrogen: NO_x , NO_3 , NO_2 , NH_4 , PO_4

Nitrogen and phosphate concentrations were measured using a 1 M KCl solution. 20 mL of 1M KCl was added to exactly 8 grams of soil in a 50 mL Greiner tube. The mixture was shaken for 2 hours using a reciprocating shaker. The supernatant resulting from the preparation of the pH measurement was filtered through a 0,45 μm glasfiber syringe filter. The concentrations of ammonium (NH_4^+), total nitrogen oxides (NO_x) and nitrite (NO_2^-) were measured using a discrete analyzer (Thermo Fisher Scientific Gallery). Nitrate (NO_3^-) concentration was derived from the NO_x and NO_2^- measurements. The moisture percentage in the soil that was derived from the freeze-drying procedures at 4.1.4 was used to calculate $\text{NO}_x\text{-N}$, $\text{NO}_3\text{-N}$, $\text{NO}_2\text{-N}$ and $\text{NH}_4\text{-N}$ in g per kg of dry soil using the following formula (similar for all measurements):

$$\text{NH}_4 - \text{N or NO}_x - \text{N or NO}_3 - \text{N or NO}_2 - \text{N or PO}_4 - \text{P} = \frac{a * M}{1000} * \frac{L}{m} * \frac{(100 + w)}{100}$$

Where:

- **$\text{NH}_4\text{-N}$, $\text{NO}_3\text{-N}$, $\text{NO}_2\text{-N}$, $\text{NO}_x\text{-N}$, $\text{PO}_4\text{-P}$** ,= nitrogen or phosphor concentrations in mg kg^{-1} dry soil
- **a** = concentration of NH_4^+ , NO_3^- , or NO_2^- measured in the diluted sample ($\mu\text{mol/L}$)
- **M** = atomic mass of N or P in g/mol
- **m** = mass of wet soil used in the suspension (g)
- **L** = volume of liquid used in suspension (ml)
- **w** = percentage of water content based on freeze-dried soil

4.1.3 Cation concentrations

Approximately 20 grams of soil was weighed using a precision balance into a pre-weighed 50 mL Greiner tube. The tubes were then placed in one of the two available freeze dryers (Heto PowerDry LL3000 and SCALA TFD5503) for 48 hours. The samples were subsequently ground in the Herzog HP-Ma automatic pulverizer. Exact weights of samples for analysis were recorded using a precision balance. The concentrations of Ca, Al, K, Na, Mg and P were measured using a ICP-OES analyzer (Perkin-Elmer Avio 500).

4.1.4 Soil organic carbon and C:N ratio

Approximately 20 grams of soil was weighed using a precision balance into a pre-weighed 50 mL Greiner tube. The tubes were then placed in one of the two available freeze dryers (Heto PowerDry LL3000 and SCALA TFD5503) for 48 hours. The weight was then measured again to determine the soil moisture content. The samples were subsequently ground in the Herzog HP-Ma automatic pulverizer. A small portion of each sample was weighed using a precision balance and transferred to silver cups. In order to measure soil organic carbon content, potential CaCO_3 was removed from the sample through acidification by placing the samples in a desiccator with a small beaker of 20ml 37%

fuming HCl underneath it for 6 hours. The percentage carbon (C) and nitrogen (N) was subsequently determined using a CN-analyzer (NA1500, Fisons Instruments), and the C:N ratio was calculated by dividing these two values.

Note that in the results some values have an * or two times ** before the value. * indicates a measurement that was in between the Limit of Quantification (LOQ) and the Below Effective Concentration (BEC). In practice this means that these values have an error of >10% and should thus be interpreted as an estimate. ** indicates a value that is below the LOQ and thus cannot be considered accurate.

4.1.5 Soil Organic Matter Content

Approximately 20 grams of soil was weighed using a precision balance into a pre-weighed 50 mL Greiner tube. The tubes were then placed in one of the two available freeze dryers (Heto PowerDry LL3000 and SCALA TFD5503) for 48 hours. The weight was then measured again to determine the soil moisture content. The samples were subsequently grinded in the Herzog HP-Ma automatic pulverizer. A portion of these soil samples were used to determine the percentage of organic matter, by measuring the weight loss after four hours of heating at 450 degrees Celsius (TGA701 Thermogravimetric Analyzer). The samples were then stepwise heated to 1000°C (550-800-1000°C), which resulted in additional organic matter mass loss at each temperature. Decrease in weight was recorded at each step as a percentage of the initial sample weight. Total soil organic matter percentage was calculated by summation of these weight losses.

5. WP 3 Forest plot data, processing and calculations

5.1. Plot layout existing field trials (WP3)

Data on forest structure and composition in semi-permanent sample plots was provided by the State Forestry Service (SBB) and consists of measurements taken over a 30-year timespan and conducted at three separate measurement censuses, using the SYHI (systematic woodstock inventories), see Table 5.1.

Table 5.1: Plot measurements by census and number of plots per location.

Location (Forest Management Unit)	Measurement years	Number of plots
Austerlitz (AUS)	1994, 2006, 2019	194
Vuursche (VUU)	1996, 2006, 2019	222
Amerongen (AML)	2002, 2012, 2024	434

In each FMU a grid was deployed of rows and columns, each with a distance of 200 meters, and at each intersection (row and column) a plot was located. Each plot received a unique code, a combination of letters (AA-ZZ; columns) and numbers (1-n; rows). In each plot, the spatial coordinate of a central tree was recorded. Variable radii were employed, varying between 5 and 20 meters depending on tree density. Facing North at the central tree and in clockwise direction in each plot ca 20 individual trees with > 5 cm DBH were identified and DBH measured. The volume of standing dead tree trunks and lying dead tree biomass were calculated. In each plot and within the plot radius trees < 5 cm DBH and a height > 50 cm were identified and counted as established recruits.

5.2 Tree growth measurements

Individual measured trees in plots of successive years were not georeferenced. As such, DBH growth of individual trees between successive measuring periods was difficult to establish. To calculate DBH growth of trees within plots Two modifications were made:

- Dead trees were deleted from the dataset;
- The dataset contained details on the dominance of individual trees: [1] Dominant, [2] Co-dominant [3], Suppressed [4], Subordinate [5] Understory. This was simplified into an alternative position coding: trees with number 1 or 2 were assigned a position code 1 (canopy trees), trees with numbers 3, 4 or 5 were assigned position code 2 (understory trees).

Although trees received a unique tree number per plot, these numbers could differ per tree in different measurement years, i.e., a tree numbered #1 in year 1 may not be the same individual (#1) in year 2. It was therefore necessary to manually identify individual trees throughout the different measurement periods. The assumption was made that trees keep the same position code through time, where (manual) alterations were applied to calculate DBH growth.

- When less than three trees of a species with a similar position level were present in a plot, the tree was identified throughout the different measurement periods by eye based on several factors: tree number and realistic growth rate according to literature. The tree number should be within a range of 5 consecutive tree numbers from the tree number of the previous year. A negative or extremely high growth rate indicates that it is a different tree.

- When more than three trees of a species with a similar position level were present in a plot, it was deemed impossible to identify individual trees and subsequently the average of these trees was calculated. Here, one 'pseudo-individual' was created for that species in that plot based on the average DBH in a plot in a measurement period.

The result is a list of DBH values of tree species with a tree position (canopy/understory) per plot, for three different measurement periods.

For each measurement, the exact day of measurement was provided. Based on this data, the number of days between measurements was calculated. This number was used to calculate the growth per year over the period in between two consecutive measurements.

Note that in the final dataset individuals are present that have no indication of position (1 or 2), but instead NA, denoted as a dot (.). This details the use of 'pseudo-individuals' that may not have the same position in the canopy, and specifically those that were derived by averaging the DBH of trees with both position 1 and position 2. As such, no position could be determined.

5.3 Allometric relations

For each measurement census and in each plot ca. 2-4 trees were selected for both DBH and height measurements in the field. Based on DBH and height allometric relations can be obtained.

For DBH-volume relations, we took DBH volume relations as established by Dolstra et al. (2019). This volume estimate is carried out for estimating wood stocks (Dolstra et al., 2010) of plots in the study area. This relation is established by the following formula to determine the spindle wood volume:

$$V_s = b_0 + b_1 * DBH + b_2 * DBH^2$$

In which,

V_s = Spindle wood volume in dm^3

b_0, b_1, b_2 = species specific constants

DBH = diameter at breast height (in cm) of individual tree

The species-specific constants (b) have been established earlier in tests using trees in the Utrecht Heuvelrug forest (Dolstra et al., 2019). This formula is applied to each individual tree and measured DBH in the plots. For some less common species, no specific constants were available. In that case the generic constants for deciduous or coniferous trees were applied, see table 5.2 for the species-specific constants.

Table 5.2: Species specific constants applied to tree volume calculations. For all other species in the database with diameter measurements the generic formula for other deciduous species (LO) or other coniferous species (NO) were applied, based on Dolstra et al. (2019).

Species	Spec_code	b ₀	b ₁	b ₂
Quercus rubra	AE	-6.01	-1.52	0.72
Betula pendula	BE	-7.02	-0.25	0.56
Fagus sylvatica	BU	5.87	-3.31	0.65
Pseudotsuga menziesii	DG	38.69	-11	1.1
Quercus robur	EI	15.53	-6.3	0.79
Pinus sylvestris	GD	-8.42	-1.58	0.76
Larix kaempferi	JL	30.78	-9.24	1.04
Other deciduous spec.	LO	6.72	-3.46	0.65
Other coniferous spec.	NO	23.68	-8.81	1.07